

SYMBOLISM OF THE MOST COMMON COLOUR COMBINATIONS ENGLISH

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to study the symbolism of the most common colour combinations English and Russian.*

Key words: symbolism, color, particular, conviviality, possible, meaning.

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена изучению символики наиболее распространенных цветовых сочетаний английского и русского языков.*

Ключевые слова: *символизм, цвет, особенность, праздничность, возможность, значение.*

The symbolism of color is inherent in all languages and has different origins. Some of the symbolic meanings are fixed in stable phrases found in one or more languages. They served as the material of this article. The purpose of this article is to study the symbolism of color meanings in English and Russian, as well as to identify its similarities and differences and, if possible, to trace the sources of this symbolism. The green color in both languages studied symbolizes freedom: green card (work permit in the USA), green channel (duty-free passage at customs), to give green light, to give green light (green street); youth: to be green (as grass), to be too green (young); nature: the green party, the Green movement.

Red color is widely used to attract attention:

A number of others follow from this meaning, in particular, danger, prohibition: red light, drive through a red light; red card, red card (in football), the Red List, Red Book. Also, the red color symbolizes special, important things, both positive and negative. In in accounting, the debt was written in red ink: to be in the red. Red symbolizes conviviality: red-letter day, red calendar day, the red carpet is spread out for important guests: red-carpet treatment.

White color is used as a symbol of purity, purity. The symbolism of white as a positive color has been inherent since the most ancient times and developed independently in these languages. There are significantly more phrases in English, such as: Whiter than white (flawless), white days (happy days), white lie (innocent lie), white-handed (respectable, honest, unblemished) in contrast to red-handed (guilty; caught in the act).

The blue color is also used as a symbol, it is associated with the sky, the unearthly world. According to M.M. Makovsky, "the blue color has long been associated with an otherworldly, unearthly world inhabited by gods and the souls of the dead".

Hence arose the meaning of "vague, incomprehensible, deceptive" and also "dreamy, romantic": blue-sky project (a project with an unknown result, meaningless). Thanks to literary works, this color is also associated with romanticism The Blue bird of happiness – The Blue bird is a symbol of dreams [2], the Blue Rose (association of Russian artists of the early twentieth century). It is also used to denote high distinction: blue ribbon, blue ribbon (symbol of high achievement) Blue blood, blue blood.

The black color symbolizes evil and characterizes the so-called phenomenon with a negative sides. Hence such expressions as: black death- black death, black dog (bad mood, despondency; green melancholy); Meaning "associated with evil" reveals coincidences of meanings in both languages in such phrases as: black art, black magic; black ingratitude - black ingratitude.

And brown in English, as well as black, is a symbol of negative phenomena: do brown (deceive), brown study (gloomy mood), browned off (irritated, angry).

Gray is a symbol of inexpressiveness, dullness: a grey day, greyness, grey weather, grey sky. The constructions in which the color designation appears in these languages are different and this indicates the independence of the origin of such symbolism and its universality: a gray day, gray weekdays, under the thumbs of the greys (at the mercy of "grayness"); gray years (a monotonous series of years);

Yellow is used as a warning symbol: the phrases yellow card, yellow card; yellow light, yellow traffic light are also known in all languages, since the symbolism of yellow as a warning signal is common everywhere. The symbolism of yellow as the color of betrayal is realized in both languages studied: In English, the phrase yellow-dog contract is used (a contract obliging workers not to join trade unions) and it, in turn, comes from the phrase yellow dog (scoundrel, scoundrel) and acts as a symbol of betrayal and treason (hence yellow-dog fund – amounts used for bribery). Thus, it can be concluded that the symbolism of one or another color designations developed in the language in two ways. It could have been preserved since ancient times, when it was used by the Indo-Europeans, or it developed later, when an object of a certain color acquired the appropriate symbolism. In the studied languages , the symbolism of color designations is implemented in the following types of constructions:

- The same values are expressed using the same color values that arose simultaneously and using the same model (most often noun + adjective), for example,
- Red Cross, Red cross; yellow card, yellow card.
- Different color designations can be used to describe the same phenomenon, for example: brown study, longing is green.
- The same color designation can be used to describe various phenomena: to be in the black – to have no debts, to be blue – to be sad;
- A number of color meanings, however, have a specific use to describe an object of a corresponding color only in one of the studied languages, for example, blue language – indecent expressions;

Literature

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